

Educational Software Package on Scheduling Algorithms for Real Time Control Applications

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Abstract— The vital aim of the real time system implementation is to catalyze development in the application of real-time systems engineering, specifically by increasing the use of scheduling algorithms. In this paper, we implement some of the most important decisions strategies in order to build an educational package for final year undergraduate students studying real time control engineering and/or master students taking subject of real time control engineering. In this package, the students will be introduced to the essential concepts of the development of real time control system; starting from providing the linear or nonlinear model that describe a control system (an AC servo motor is considered here as an example), selecting proper sampling rate, design of conventional controller like a PID, ending up with determination of the execution time and the application of scheduling algorithms like (Rate Monotonic-Scheduling (RMS) and Earliest Dead line First (EDF))for multitasking operation. In order to develop the required algorithms the students will be introduced to some useful advanced MATLAB/Simulink functions like S function and state flow diagram.

Index Terms— real-time system, scheduling algorithm, AC servo motor, multitasking operation, Rate Monotonic Scheduling (RMS), Earliest Dead line First (EDF), PID.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last two decades, we have witnessed an explosive growth of real-time and embedded systems being used in our daily life. Current applications of computers in control, multimedia, signal processing, communications, *etc.* set very hard timing demands on real-time systems. Regardless of the high computing power, tasks that are executed by those computers need to be scheduled in such a way that they have better requested timing properties and utilization. Real-time scheduling deals with the above-mentioned problem.

Recently, many research work on real time scheduling have been recognized; in [1], parallel-machine scheduling problem was described for electronic manufacturing industry considering past-sequence dependent (*psd*) delivery times and learning effect to obtain an optimal solution. A pseudo-polynomial algorithm is developed in [2] for the case of scheduling with a fixed number of UIs (time intervals during which the machine is not allowed to process jobs). The scheduling problem of an important class of large-scale Grid

applications was addressed in [3]. It characterized by a huge number of homogeneous, concurrent, and computationally intensive tasks which are the main sources of performance, cost, and storage bottlenecks. A new formulation had been proposed in [3] of this problem based on a cooperative distributed game-theory-based method. For flight scheduling which is a real-time optimization problem, [4] presents a description of the problem in which the total delay minutes of passengers are considered as the optimization objective and which takes into account available resources and the estimated cost of airlines.

It is known that a real-time control system is a system in which the resulting performance depends not only on the correctness of the single control actions but also on the time at which the actions are produced. The operating system is the major architectural component responsible for ensuring a timely execution of all the tasks having some timing requirements. In the presence of several concurrent activities running on a single processor, the objective of a real-time kernel is to ensure that each activity completes its execution within its deadline. Notice that this is very different than minimizing the average response times of a set of tasks [5].

Depending on the consequences caused by a missed deadline, real-time activities can be classified into hard and soft tasks. A real-time task is said to be hard if missing a deadline may have catastrophic consequences on the controlled system, and is said to be soft if missing a deadline causes performance degradation but does not jeopardize the correct system behavior [6].

Most of the control activities, such as signal acquisition, filtering, sensory data processing, action planning, and actuator control, are typically implemented as periodic tasks activated at specific rates imposed by the application requirements. When a set T of n periodic tasks has to be concurrently executed on the same processor, the problem is to verify whether all tasks can complete their execution within their timing constraints. There are several approaches dedicated to handle this problem like classical cyclic scheduling approach, a fixed priority-based scheduler, rate monotonic scheduling (RMS), and earliest deadline first (EDF) algorithms [5].

Educational package on real time scheduling had been proved to provide students with a visual insight into real-time system properties and scheduling algorithms [7]. It illustrates the behavior and analysis of scheduling algorithms with fixed priorities over a mixture of periodic tasks. In our educational package; we will focus on RMS and EDF approaches, as will be demonstrated in this paper. Scheduling of three tasks is considered as shown in Fig.1. Each task consists of applying a PID controller to AC servo system.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section one is an Introduction; Section Two presents the basic ideas on real time scheduling techniques. Section Three describes the AC servo system which is considered in the simulation. Section Four illustrates the development and application of the algorithms. And Section Five gives some conclusions.

a.

b.

Fig.1. schematic diagram of scheduling: a. For three tasks.
b. For each task.

II. REAL TIME SCHEDULING TECHNIQUES

A hard real-time system must execute a set of concurrent real-time tasks in such a way that all time-critical tasks meet their specified deadlines. Every task needs computational and data resources to complete the job. The scheduling problem is concerned with the allocation of the resources to satisfy the timing constraints.

Schedulability test often used by dynamic schedulers to determine whether a given set of ready tasks can be scheduled to meet their deadlines or not. Scheduling techniques may be preemptive or non-preemptive techniques, Tasks are usually assigned with priorities at times it is necessary to run a certain task that has a higher priority before another task although it is running. Therefore, the running task is interrupted for some time and resumed later when the priority task has finished its execution; this is called preemptive scheduling, if this interruption not allowed this will called non-preemptive [8]. Two types of scheduling algorithms and their schedulability criteria are explained in the following.

A. Rate monotonic Scheduling (RMS)Algorithm

Rate monotonic algorithm is a dynamic preemptive algorithm built on static priorities. The rate monotonic algorithm allocates static priorities based on task periods. Here task period is the time after which the tasks repeat and inverse of period is task arrival rate. For example, a task with a period of 10ms is repeated after every 10ms.

The task with the shortest period acquires the highest priority, and the task with the longest period gets the lowest static priority. At run time, the dispatcher chooses the task with the highest priority for execution.

Given the computation time, C_i , and period, T_i , for task i , its CPU utilization can be calculated with the following equation [5]:

$$U_i = C_i / T_i \quad (1)$$

For rate monotonic scheduling, the processor utilization for n tasks has been shown to be the following:

$$U(n) = n \left(2^{\frac{1}{n}} - 1 \right) \quad (2)$$

According to RMS a set of periodic, independent task can be scheduled to meet their deadlines, if the sum of their utilization factors of the n tasks is given as below:

$$\frac{C_1}{T_1} + \dots + \frac{C_n}{T_n} \leq U(n) = n \left(2^{\frac{1}{n}} - 1 \right) \quad (3)$$

As the number of tasks increases, the scheduling bound converges to $\ln 2$ (69%) [5]. We will use this value for the rate monotonic schedulability test. If this equality is satisfied, all of the tasks will always meet their deadlines. If the total utilization calculates to greater than 100%, the system will have scheduling problems.

B. Earliest Deadline-First (EDF) Algorithm

EDF algorithm is an optimal dynamic preemptive algorithm based on dynamic priorities. In which after any significant event, the task with the earliest deadline is assigned the highest dynamic priority. A significant event in a system can be blocking of a task, invocation of a task, completion of a task, etc.

Fig.2. RMS algorithm flowchart.

The processor utilization can up to 100% with EDF, even when the task periods are not multiples of the smallest periods. The dispatcher operates in the same way as the dispatcher for the RMS algorithm according to [5]:

$$\frac{C_1}{T_1} + \dots + \frac{C_n}{T_n} \leq U(n) = 1 \quad (4)$$

There are several ways to implement these multitasking problems. In our educational package we will use MATLAB/Simulink using S-function, as will be described in Section Four.

Fig.3. EDF algorithm flowchart.

I. THE SERVO MOTOR POISONING SYSTEM

In this paper, each of the three tasks contains an AC servo motor positioning system. In this part, the students will be introduced to the modelling of nonlinear friction function as well as the linear model of the servo system. The purpose is to learn how to deal with the actual system in precise. Different numerical values of the parameters of the positioning system will be considered for each of the three tasks. Nevertheless, the structure of combining the linear and the friction parts is applied for all.

A. Linear Dynamic Model of the Servo Motor

The dynamic behavior of the considered electric AC servomotor driven positioning system can be described by the following second-order nonlinear differential equation [9]:

$$S^2 + Sy = \alpha_i K_i u - F_f \quad (5)$$

where y is the servomotor's displacement, u is inputs to the servomotor drive, F_f is friction force and K_i and α_i are positive constants, which relate with motor dynamics and mechanical system. The object parameters K_i and α_i include velocity and current controller parameters.

B. The learning based stick-slip friction model

The learning-based stick-slip friction model has been used for handling frictions and disturbances. It is assumed to be described mathematically as follows [10]:

$$F_{f(v,t)} = F_{slip}(v)a(v) + F_{stick}(u)[1 - a(v)] \quad (6)$$

$$a(v) = \begin{cases} 0, & |v(t)| \leq \alpha_s \\ 1, & |v(t)| > \alpha_s \end{cases} \quad \alpha_s > 0 \quad (7)$$

The sticking friction is modeled as follows:

$$F_{stick}(u) = \begin{cases} F_s^+, & u(k) \geq F_s^+ \\ u(k), & F_s^- < u(k) < F_s^+ \\ 0, & u(k) \leq F_s^- \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

The constants F_s^+ and F_s^- give the positive and negative limits on the static friction forces, respectively. Generally, they are not equal in magnitude, and the model should consider this asymmetry.

The slipping function F_{slip} provides values of the friction at non-zero velocity and is given by [11]:

$$F_{slip}(v) = F_d^+(v)b(v) + F_d^-(v)b(-v) \quad (9)$$

$$b(v) = \begin{cases} 1, & v(t) > 0 \\ 0, & v(t) \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$$F_d^+(v) = F_s^+ - \Delta F^+ [1 - e^{-(v/v_{cr}^+)}] + \sigma^+ v \quad (11)$$

$$F_d^-(v) = F_s^- - \Delta F^- [1 - e^{-(v/v_{cr}^-)}] + \sigma^- v \quad (12)$$

where ΔF^+ and ΔF^- are the respective drops from the static to the kinetic force level; v_{cr}^+ and v_{cr}^- are the critical Stribeck velocities, σ^+ and σ^- are the viscous friction coefficients. The static parameters F_d^+ , F_s^+ , and v as well as the dynamic parameters σ^+ and σ^- are obtained using off-line Genetic Algorithm (GA) identification methodology. The identified parameters are used in Eqs. 8, 11, and 12 to develop the required stick slip friction model [10].

II. DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ALGORITHMS

The implementation of the proposed algorithm is accomplished by adapting both the graphical elements in MATLAB/Simulink and some source code.

A. The friction model

A State-flow chart as a finite state machine is implemented in this work to perform the action of stick slip friction model. A *finite state machine* is a representation of an event-driven (reactive) system. In an event-driven system, the system makes a transition from one state (mode) to another, if the condition defining the change is true. The applied truth table functions implement logical decision-making behaviour that can be called in an action language. State flow truth tables contain conditions, decisions, and actions arranged in a certain order. The resulting table describes the logic necessary to control the behaviour of the stick slip friction model. Each of the conditions entered in the Condition column must evaluate to true (nonzero value) or false (zero value). Outcomes for each condition are specified as T (true), F (false), or $-$ (true or false). Each of the decision columns combines an outcome for each condition with a logical AND

into a compound condition that is referred to as a decision. In a truth table one decision is evaluated at a time, starting with first decision. If one of the decisions is true, its action is performed and truth table execution is complete [12].

B. The PID controller

In this part, the student will be introduced to the basic rules of designing a simple PID controller, followed by proper selection of the sampling interval for simulation. The student will be familiar with the fact that the proportional controller P will have the effect of reducing the rise time and will reduce but never eliminate the steady-state error. An integral control I will have the effect of eliminating the steady-state error for a constant or step input, but it may make the transient response slower. A derivative control D will have the effect of increasing the stability of the system, reducing the overshoot, and improving the transient response. In our experiments with the AC servo system, we start by tuning the gain part K . The recommended range of tuning K is found to be between 5 to 15. Accordingly T_r , E_{ss} and T_s will increase as K decreases, while the overshoot will decrease. Then in order to eliminate E_{ss} , T_i is manipulated till we get the best possible result. T_D will only be tuned to ensure that the controller is not sluggish.

By suitable selection of the simulation sampling rate h from 0.0001 to 0.001 seconds, we notice that the system can be simulated accurately without any noticeable difference in T_s , T_r and E_{ss} .

In order to consider practical application, an integral control scheme [13] is added to the closed loop controlled system to ensure zero tracking error, as shown in Fig.4. $K_{If} > 0$ is an additional integral action that improves the performance at low frequencies. Moreover, the phase advance term $s + K_{If}$ maintains wide bandwidth from the PID controller.

Fig.4. The Integral-robust controller scheme [13].

To implement a continuous-time control law, such as a PID controller in a digital computer, it is necessary to approximate the derivatives and the integral that appear in the control law. The implemented method can be described as follows [14]:

The proportional term is

$$P = K(y_{sp} - y) \quad (13)$$

This term is implemented simply by replacing the continuous variables with their sampled versions. Hence,

$$P(t_k) = K(b_p y_{sp}(t_k) - y(t_k)) \quad (14)$$

where (t_k) denotes the sampling instants, i.e., the times when the computer reads the analog input, b_p is a fraction of the command signal acts on the proportional part. The integral term is given by

$$I(t) = \frac{K}{T_i} \int_0^t e(s) ds \quad (15)$$

It follows that

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = \frac{K}{T_i} e \quad (16)$$

Approximating the derivative by a forward difference gives

$$\frac{I(t_{k+1}) - I(t_k)}{h} = \frac{K}{T_i} e(t_k) \quad (17)$$

Then, the following recursive equation for the integral term can be obtained

$$I(t_{k+1}) = I(t_k) + \frac{Kh}{T_i} e(t_k) \quad (18)$$

The derivative term is given by Eq. (19), i.e.

$$\frac{T_d}{N} \frac{dD}{dt} + D = -KT_d \frac{dy}{dt} \quad (19)$$

The derivative in Eq. (19) is approximated by a backward difference, the following equation is obtained:

$$\frac{T_d}{N} \frac{dD(t_k) - D(t_{k-1})}{h} + D(t_k) = -KT_d \frac{dy(t_k) - y(t_{k-1})}{h} \quad (20)$$

This can be rewritten as

$$D(t_k) = \frac{T_d}{T_d + Nh} D(t_{k-1}) - \frac{KT_d N}{T_d + Nh} (y(t_k) - y(t_{k-1})) \quad (21)$$

The total PID action will be the sum of the three Eqs. (14), (18) and (21). In the followings, different experiments have been conducted to demonstrate the various issues of the

developed educational package. The values of K , T_i and T_d found to be 0.96, 0.12 and 0.049 respectively.

C. Scheduling

Consider the following example in which three tasks T_1, T_2 , and T_3 with worst case computation times $C_1 = 10 \text{ ms}$, $C_2 = 8 \text{ ms}$, and $C_3 = 5 \text{ ms}$. The three tasks will have to be periodically executed on a processor with periods $T_1 = 25 \text{ ms}$, $T_2 = 50 \text{ ms}$, and $T_3 = 100 \text{ ms}$. We define a MATLAB function utilization for testing this sufficient condition for RMS and EDF schedulability. The function should take a task set object T as argument and return the utilization u , and a Boolean value s , where the s flag indicate that the set of task are schedulable or not (i.e. $s=0$ not schedulable and $s=1$ schedulable), such that indicating whether the condition is satisfied or not. For the example above we see that $u = 0.61$ and $s = 1$, and the resulted scheduling graph is as shown in Fig.5.

Let the period of task T_2 be changed from 50 ms to 40 ms , then the previous schedule remain valid because $u = 0.65$ and $s = 1$, as shown in Fig.6.

Fig.5. Example 1, task set scheduling graph.

Fig.6. Task 2 modified period scheduling graph.

And by using EDF algorithm we see that the above example is also schedulable with the same results due to that $u \leq 1$. Also we should notice that the system response become stable in both periods (i.e. $T_2 = 50 \text{ ms}$ and $T_2 = 40 \text{ ms}$) due to that K , T_i and T_d are chosen to satisfy the stability condition. the student should also notice the tasks periods are used in tuning process of the PID and must be chosen to satisfy the stability condition also as well the schedulability condition. Figures 7 and 8 illustrate the mentioned examples.

Consider another example with the following parameters:

Name	C ms	T ms
task1	2	10
task2	4	15
task3	10	35

Using EDF algorithm we have $u=0.7524$ and $s=1$ which indicate also to that the task set is also schedulable, the schedule graph for the above example is shown in Fig. 9. Also we should notice the response of the system where one of the servos is stable and the other two are not as shown in Fig. 10.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig.7. Response of the system's servos ($T_2=50$ ms). a. Response of the first servo. b. Response of the second servo. c. Response of the third servo.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig.8. Response of the system's servos ($T_2=40$ ms). a. Response of the first servo. b. Response of the second servo. c. Response of the third servo.

Fig.9. Example 2, task set scheduling graph.

If we increase the worst case execution time (WCET) of task3 from 10ms to 18ms, we get $u= 0.9810$ and $s=1$ that means the task set are not schedulable. The same result is also valid for RMS algorithm because the utilization parameter $u \leq n(2^{1/n} - 1)$ where n is the number of tasks. The schedule graph of the modified task 3 WCET is shown in Fig. 11.

The student should also noticed that even though if the task set is schedulable using either algorithms, the system response may be unstable which is something must be taken into consideration, because the task period used in tuning of PID to reflect real world, that is in real world tasks interference may occur and led to system instability or performance degradation.

Fig.10. Response of the system's servos. a. Response of the first servo. b. Response of the second servo. c. Response of the third servo.

Fig.11. Modified task 3 WCET scheduling graph.

III. CONCLUSION

The study of real-time control systems demands complex and expensive laboratory conditions. This fact motivated the

development of simulation tools by which real-time control system properties could be presented on a PC. In the first part of the package the student will be introduced to the modeling of an AC servo system followed by the design of a simple PID controller. In the modeling part, the stick slip friction model is developed using state flow diagram. Then the obtained friction model is combined with a simplified servo system model in order to have a closer representation of the actual system. The second part of our package is dealing with construction of two scheduling procedures. It considers three periodic tasks. Each task consists of an AC servo positioning system. The tasks are assumed to be with fixed priorities and hard deadlines. The approach to the solution is to use a combination of the RMS or EDF algorithm that is based on server tasks. The tool enables a simple definition of input task sets, the simulation definitions and properties, the selection of desired algorithms and their properties and the selection of related evaluation parameters. Usage of a graphical demonstration of results increases program facilities.

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